

2. RLGS profiles of Nipponbare and Koshihikari were highly similar. However, the cultivars were distinguished based on the presence and absence of particular spots in the enclosed area (Kawase 1994). Arrow heads indicate the spots unique to each of the two cultivars compared.

Additionally, 24 and 25 spots were found unique to Nipponbare and Koshihikari, respectively. The GS value was calculated as 0.980.

The RLGS method can be a powerful fingerprinting technique for estimating genetic diversity in rice as well as for identifying cultivars.

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Character expression of a rice dwarf mutant with lax panicle

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A dwarf mutant with lax panicle was induced from the parent cultivar Fujiminori by 200 Gy of X-ray irradiation. The mutant exhibits leaf rolling during the early vegetative phase until the appearance of the 6th or 7th leaf. Inheritance of this mutant trait

was studied from an F₂ segregation involving a cross between the dwarf mutant and the parent cultivar. The F₁ was normal and the F₂ segregated into 103 normal plants and 39 dwarf plants, giving a good fit to a 3:1 ratio ($\chi^2 = 0.460$, $P = 0.498$). Pleiotropic action of the dwarf mutant gene appears to be responsible for the lax panicles and rolled leaves. Panicle density is a complex character, which consists of many component characters such as spikelet number, panicle length, and number of branches (Futsuhara et al 1979). Panicle laxness in this mutant could be attributed to the decrease in total spikelets and branches, especially secondary branches (see table).

Rolled leaf is a marker trait that can be used in selecting dwarf mutant types during juvenile stage.

To determine the annual and seasonal variations in various agronomic traits, the dwarf mutant and its parent cultivar were tested in 1992 and 1994. The rice plants were raised under two seeding times (early and late seedings) only in 1994.

The dwarf mutant showed different responses to various seeding conditions (see table). The difference in panicle density between parent and mutant grown under late seeding condition was not significant. Seed fertility of the mutant, which was significantly less than that of the parent

Related characters of panicle density in a dwarf mutant with lax panicles and its parent cultivar, Fujiminori.^a

Year	Seeding time	Cultivar and strain	Culm length (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Panicle density ^b	Spikelets (no.)	Fertility (%)	Primary branch (no.)	Primary branch length (cm)	Secondary branches (no.)	Rachis length (cm)
1992	Normal seeding	Fujiminori	88.0	24.1	1.58	158.4	96.0	10.8	8.0	32.8	18.7
		Dwarf mutant	74.8**	21.6*	1.11*	58.6**	66.2**	8.3**	7.3	16.5**	17.2
1994	Early seeding	Fujiminori	95.3	21.8	1.24	111.5	89.5	10.5	6.3	18.3	16.6
		Dwarf mutant	84.2**	18.8*	1.01**	68.1**	52.1**	7.2**	6.8	11.3**	12.7**
1994	Late seeding	Fujiminori	62.2	14.0	1.10	47.7	87.6	5.8	6.0	6.6	8.6
		Dwarf mutant	52.6**	12.8	1.09	39.9	34.5**	6.2	4.7*	5.1	8.7

^a* and ** = significant at the 1 and 0.1% level, respectively. ^b Panicle density = no. of spikelets/total length of rachis and primary branches (in cm) (Futsuhara et al 1979).

cultivar under all three conditions, was further reduced under late seeding condition (during an abnormally hot summer). Premature heading occurred in all the mutant plants grown under late seeding condition. Most of the panicles with premature heading showed malformed floral organs such as degenerated ovary,

multi-ovary, and long empty glumes. Late sowing also promoted premature heading. The results indicate that heat stress tolerance was depressed and premature heading was enhanced in the dwarf mutant.

Induced dwarf mutants with simultaneous changes in many traits are being used

in developmental genetic research to understand pleiotropic gene action.

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Genetic differentiation between Japanese lowland and upland rices

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Upland and lowland varieties are cultivated under different conditions in Japan. Lowland rice with useful agronomic traits is a major crop. In contrast, upland rice, useful as a genetic source of stress resistance to blast, is regarded as a minor crop. Thus, diagnostic genetic markers to evaluate upland rice will be useful to help improve resistance in modern rice varieties.

Isozyme genotypes were surveyed among Japanese lowland and upland traditional cultivars. Seventeen isozyme loci were monitored, and different genotypes were scored. A total of 27 genotypes were recognized, 16 for lowland rice and 13 for upland cultivars. Genotypic diversity for upland cultivars was 0.072, which is surprisingly higher than that of lowland cultivars (0.020). Such high genotypic diversity could not be seen from the data of Glaszmann (1987). Four hundred and fifty lowland and 200 upland cultivars were classified either as japonica or indica using discriminant score based on 11 loci (Ishikawa et al 1991, Sano and Morishima

1991). Except for five lowland and five upland cultivars classified as indicas, the rest of the cultivars were japonicas (Table 1). The 10 indicas were characterized with allele 3 for *Pgd1*, which is not common among other cultivars in Japan. Characteristics of the indica cultivars, such as short apiculus hair (APH) averaging 0.36 ± 0.11 mm, slender hull type represented by hull

Table 1. Genotypic variation for *Pgd* among Japanese lowland and upland rices.

Varietal type	<i>Pgd1-1</i>	<i>Pgd1-2</i>	<i>Pgd1-3</i>
Lowland			
Indica	0	0	5
Japonica	445	0	0
Upland			
Indica	1	0	4
Japonica	26	169	0

length-width ratio (L/W; av of 2.86 ± 0.14), and positive phenol reaction (Table 2), however, seemed to point to the cultivars' common origin.

Allele 2 for *Pgd1*, which is never observed in lowland rices, is also a remarkable diagnostic allele for specifying upland varietal groups. Upland cultivars can be classified into three groups based on *Pgd* and other trait combinations.

Group 1: characterized by the presence of allele 1 and represents longer APH (0.65 ± 0.12 mm) and round hull type (L/W; 2.14 ± 0.16) same as 445 lowland cultivars (APH; 0.72 ± 0.19 mm, L/W; 2.09 ± 0.34). However, only 19% of cultivars in this group showed positive phenol reaction.

Group 2: characterized by the presence of allele 2 and represents slightly shorter

Table 2. Morphological and physiological characteristics of Japanese lowland and upland varietal groups having different alleles for *Pgd*.

Group	Allele	Cultivars (no.)	Apiculus hair length Mean ± SD (mm)		L/W Mean ± SD (mm)	Phenol reaction ^a	
						Cultivars (no.) +	-
Lowland							
Japonica	<i>Pgd1-1</i>	445	0.72 ± 0.19	2.09 ± 0.34	32	413	
Indica ^b	<i>Pgd1-3</i>	5	0.37 ± 0.12	2.79 ± 0.16	4	1	
Upland							
Japonica A	<i>Pgd1-1</i>	26	0.65 ± 0.12	2.14 ± 0.16	5	21	
Japonica B	<i>Pgd1-2</i>	169	0.44 ± 0.14	2.38 ± 0.21	131	38	
Indica ^b	<i>Pgd1-3</i>	5	0.34 ± 0.13	2.98 ± 0.19	4	1	

^a+ = hull of cultivars blackened. - = hull did not blacken. ^bTotal of 10 indica cultivars were found. Av APH and L-W ratios were 0.96 ± 0.11 and 2.8 ± 0.14, respectively.